

INTERFACIAL ADHESION AND MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF NATURAL FIBRE COMPOSITES: EFFECT OF SURFACE ENERGY AND PHYSICAL ADHESION

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1 Introduction

Natural fibres are a realistic and ecological alternative to synthetic fibres as reinforcement of polymer composite materials due to their low cost, environmental friendliness, natural abundance, and particular mechanical properties. The latter allows the design of composite materials to meet specific mechanical properties. For instance, bamboo exhibits a combination of low density (~1.4 g/cm³) and high stiffness (~43 GPa) and strength (~800MPa), while coir fibres are not very strong and stiff, but exhibit high strain to failure (~ 40%) [1].

However, the hydrophilic nature of various natural fibres produces low interfacial interactions with certain important hydrophobic thermoplastic matrices, such as polyethylene and polypropylene, leading to a poor interfacial strength and reducing their potential as reinforcing agent of composites.

When a composite structure is loaded, the load is transferred from the matrix to the fibres mainly through shear stresses at the interface. Load transfer increases with strong bonds, thus improving the composite strength. The adhesion at the interface can be described as a combination of physical adhesion (related to wettability), chemical bonding, and mechanical interlocking. The wettability and compatibility of the fibre and the matrix can be assessed by analysis of their surface energies. This can be done by measuring contact angles, which is a quantitative measure of solid-liquid molecular interactions.

In this study, the wetting behaviour of bamboo (*Guadua Angustifolia*), and thermoplastic matrices (polyvinylidene fluoride PVDF, polypropylene PP and grafted maleic anhydride polypropylene MAPP) is characterized with the Wilhelmy technique. The

molecular-kinetic theory MKT of wetting is used to interpret the contact angle data from dynamic experiments. Surface energy components are estimated by using the acid-base approach. The fibre surface is characterized by XPS (X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy) in order to have more information about functional groups at the fibre surface and their interactions at the composite interfaces. Furthermore, the surface of the fibres has been altered in order to change the surface energy components (using a chitosan coating treatment).

In order to determine the quality of the composite interfaces, single fibre pull-out tests and transverse three point bending (T3PB) tests are performed on unidirectional composites to measure interfacial shear strength and interfacial strength respectively.

2 Methodology

2.1 Materials

Technical bamboo fibers of the species *Guadua angustifolia* were extracted from bamboo culms with a purely mechanical extraction process in the Department of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering (MTM) at KU Leuven. With the aim to smoothen the lignin at the fiber surface, bamboo fibers were also further put in an autoclave under 3 bars of pressure at 150 °C for one hour (for more details on this procedure see [2]).

Polypropylene, 0.3% maleic anhydride grafted polypropylene and polyvinylidene fluoride (Solef 1008) were obtained from Propex, Dupont, and Solvay respectively in the form of films. These films were washed with a detergent (RBS-35 from Chemical Products) at a concentration of 4% v/v in water during one hour, and next rinsed in ultrapure water at 90°C for one hour.

2.2 Determination of the fibre perimeter

The method applied to determine the fibre perimeter is based on the same principle as the Wilhelmy technique. In this case, however, instead of the contact angle the perimeter is sought. When a liquid with 0° contact angle is used, the Wilhelmy equation, $F = p\gamma_l \cos \theta$, becomes:

$$F = p\gamma_l \quad (1)$$

where F is the measured force, p is the fibre perimeter, and γ the liquid surface tension.

At relatively low speeds, very low surface tension hexane is assumed to have a contact angle of 0° with virtually all substrates [2].

2.3 Bamboo fibres absorption measurement

The weight of liquid absorbed by the sample was measured with the electronic microbalance option (Krüss K100) to a resolution of 1 µg.

2.4 Surface characterization: X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

XPS analyses were performed on a Kratos Axis Ultra spectrometer (Kratos Analytical UK) equipped with a monochromatized aluminium X-ray source (powered at 10 mA and 15 kV).

One single fibre was cantilevered fixed on a flat stainless steel trough with a piece of double sided isolative tape. This way of mounting insures that the fibre surface only was analyzed but not its surrounding. The troughs, holding each one fibre sample, were then inserted in the multispecimen holder.

The pressure in the analysis chamber was about 10-6 Pa. The angle between the normal to the sample surface and the direction of photoelectrons collection was about 0°. Analyses were performed in the hybrid lens mode with the slot aperture and the iris drive position set at 0.5, the resulting analysed area was 700 µm x 300 µm. The pass energy of the hemispherical analyser was set at 160 eV for the survey scan and 40 eV for narrow scans. In the latter conditions, the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the Ag 3d5/2 peak of a standard silver sample was about 0.9 eV.

Charge stabilisation was achieved by using the Kratos Axis Ultra device. The electron source was operated with a filament current between 1.9 and 2.1 A and a bias of -1.1 eV. The charge balance plate

was set between -3.3 and -3.9V.

The following sequence of spectra was recorded: survey spectrum, C1s, O1s, N1s, Ca2p, Si2p, Na1s, P2p and C1s again to check for charge stability as a function of time and the absence of degradation of the sample during the analysis. The C-(C,H) component of the C 1s peak of carbon was fixed to 284.8 eV to set the binding energy scale.

The data treatment was performed with the CasaXPS program (Casa Software Ltd., UK). Mole fractions were calculated using peak areas normalised on the basis of acquisition parameters after a linear background subtraction, and consideration of experimental sensitivity factors and transmission factors (depending on kinetic energy, analyser pass energy and lens combination) provided by the manufacturer.

C1s spectra were decomposed with a Gaussian/Lorentzian (70/30) product function, by constraining the FWHM's of all components to be equal. See [2] for more information.

2.5 Contact angle measurements

Advancing and receding contact angles of various test liquids on the polymer films were measured under controlled conditions: temperature of 20 °C and humidity of 60%, with a Krüss K100 tensiometer using the Wilhelmy technique. The equilibrium contact angle is estimated by using the equation proposed by Andrieu et al.[3], corresponding to the average of the cosines of the advancing (θ_{adv}) and receding (θ_{rec}) angles, as shown in equation 2.

$$\cos \theta_0 = 0.5 \cos \theta_{adv} + 0.5 \cos \theta_{rec} \quad (2)$$

For the natural fibers, the same method was used. However, only advancing angles could be measured due to surface irregularities [2].

2.6 Surface energy components

Surface energies and components of the surface energies of the fibers and matrices can be estimated using the contact angle data of various test liquids on the fibers and matrices. Van Oss, Chaudhury and Good developed a model that considers the acid-base interaction between molecules, dividing the surface energy into a Lifshitz-van der Waals (γ^{LW}), an acid (γ^+) and a base (γ^-) component [4], as is shown in equation 2.

$$\gamma_s = \gamma_s^{LW} + 2\sqrt{\gamma_s^+ \gamma_s^-} \quad (3)$$

The work of adhesion, W_a , is described as the work required to disjoint a unit area of the solid-liquid interface, and it is defined in terms of surface free energies by the Dupré equation [5]:

$$W_a = \gamma_l + \gamma_s - \gamma_{sl} \quad (4)$$

Where γ_s is the surface energy of the solid, γ_l is the surface energy of the liquid or matrix and γ_{sl} is the interfacial energy.

The calculation and analysis of the work of adhesion (W_a), spreading coefficient (S), and interfacial energy (γ_{sl}) for fibres as substrate with different polymers, allow us to predict the physical adhesion and compatibility of the composite systems.

$$S = \gamma_s - (\gamma_l + \gamma_{sl}) \quad (5)$$

$$\gamma_{sl} = \gamma_s^{LW} + \gamma_l^{LW} + 2[(\gamma_s^+ \gamma_s^-)^{1/2} + (\gamma_l^+ \gamma_l^-)^{1/2} - (\gamma_s^{LW} \gamma_l^{LW})^{1/2} - (\gamma_s^+ \gamma_l^-)^{1/2} - (\gamma_s^- \gamma_l^+)^{1/2}] \quad (6)$$

2.7 Fitting procedure MKT

The parameters of the wetting kinetics are obtained by curve fitting from the correlation plot of experimental dynamic contact angle values and wetting velocity. The procedure followed by Vega et al. [6] was adapted in fitting the data using the molecular-kinetic theory.

$$v = 2K_0 \lambda \sinh \left[\frac{\gamma \lambda^2}{2kT} (\cos \theta_0 - \cos \theta) \right] \quad (7)$$

Where λ is the average length of each molecular displacement, k is the Boltzmann constant, T the absolute temperature, γ the surface tension of the liquid, and θ_0 the static contact angle at $v = 0$. The complete derivation of this model is presented by Blake [7].

2.7 Flexural testing

Unidirectional composites were prepared by compression molding of stacks of prepregs consisting of technical fibres, compressed between thermoplastic films. The applied pressure was 20 bar and temperatures of 175°C and 200°C were used depending on the polymer used. Flexural three point bending tests were performed on a universal testing machine (Instron 4426) based on ASTM D790, both

in transverse direction to obtain a value for the interface strength and in longitudinal direction to evaluate composite strength.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Dynamic wetting

Since there are several phenomena affecting the wetting behaviour of natural fibres, it was questioned whether usual experimental techniques (Wilhelmy, drop geometry analysis), which are commonly thought to supply information on equilibrium properties of the fibre's surface, are really doing so [2]. Fig.1 shows the dynamic contact angle for bamboo fibre as a function of wetting velocity for four different liquids. Autoclave smoothed bamboo fibre follows the expected MKT behaviour closely.

The results indicate that the advancing angles are speed-dependent in all the test liquids conforming well to the prediction of the MKT over the entire experimental speed range (see Fig. 1). The quality of the fit to Eq. (8) reveals good agreement between the experimental and the calculated values of the dynamic contact angle θ .

Fig.1. The dynamic contact angle for bamboo fibre vs. wetting velocity for water (open squares), ethylene glycol (filled triangles), diiodomethane (open tilted squares), and benzyl alcohol (filled squares).

The advancing contact angles of water, ethylene glycol (EG), and methylene iodide (MI) on untreated and chitosan treated bamboo fibers and the equilibrium contact angle of these liquids on thermoplastic films according to the approach of Andrieu et al.[3] are shown in table 1.

Material	Water	EG	MI
Bamboo	60.3 ± 2.3	42.8 ± 0.8	47.9 ± 1.1
Chitosan	98.0 ± 4.1	64.1 ± 5.8	67.3 ± 4.2
PP	86.0 ± 1.1	49.4 ± 1.7	57.7 ± 1.0
MAPP	82.8 ± 0.7	65.3 ± 0.9	61.1 ± 0.6
PVDF	66.2 ± 0.3	36.0 ± 0.4	32.8 ± 0.3

Table 1. Measured contact angles.

3.2 Surface chemical composition

Figure 2 shows the XPS results regarding surface chemical constituents of both autoclave-treated and non-treated technical bamboo fibres obtained from the decomposition of the high resolution carbon 1s spectrum for each fibre. Lignin content on the fibre surface was analyzed by determining the oxygen-to-carbon atomic ratio, and the relative concentration of the C1 component. The results clearly indicate that technical bamboo surface constituents are close to our references for lignin, indicating that bamboo technical fibres may be homogeneously covered with lignin and possibly some other molecules, but not with cellulose. On autoclave treatment, the surface chemistry does not change.

Figure 2. C1/C ratios versus O/C ratios for chemical groups at the surface of bamboo fibers [2]. Theoretical values for cellulose and lignin according to Shchukarev [8].

3.3 Wetting parameters and evaluation of the interface

The surface tension components of the solids were determined from the advancing (static) and equilibrium contact angles of the liquids on the solids (see Table 2). According to the acid-base theory [9], the total surface tension of the bamboo fibres was estimated to be 38.82 mN/m, with an acid and base contribution of 0.28 mN/m and 10.13 mN/m respectively and a total polar component of

3.37 mN/m (see Table 2). Accordingly, the fibre's surface is relatively hydrophobic and a Lewis base; this means that a strong acidic Lewis matrix would give the best physical adhesion performance. For optimal physical adhesion, the surface energy of the solid substrate should be as high as possible, the two phases should have the same Lifshitz-van der Waals components and the acidic component of the substrate should be equal to the basic component of the liquid and vice versa [5].

Material	γ^{tot} (mJ/m ²)	γ^{LW} (mJ/m ²)	γ^{ab} (mJ/m ²)
Bamboo	38.82 ± 0.76	35.44 ± 0.06	3.37 ± 0.57
Bam-chitosan	25.13 ± 1.42	24.39 ± 1.38	0.74 ± 0.44
PP	30.87 ± 0.52	29.90 ± 0.47	0.97 ± 0.20
MAPP	29.07 ± 0.37	28.52 ± 0.31	0.56 ± 0.20
PVDF	34.64 ± 0.53	31.16 ± 0.47	3.48 ± 0.23

Table 2. Surface energy components.

As expected, PVDF possesses higher acidity among the three examined matrices due to the different electro-negativities of carbon, fluorine, and hydrogen [10]. Accordingly, the total surface energy of PVDF is higher than that of PP and MAPP, with a higher polar fraction.

For the case of PP, we found a small anomaly in the magnitude of the polar surface energy component, which is expected to be zero, since pure PP is a nonpolar polymer. This effect may be related to aging processes or surface contamination.

The work of physical adhesion (W_a) and the spreading coefficient (S), were calculated for the different materials by using equation 4 and 5. Figure 3 shows the calculated W_a and S values with bamboo as the substrate.

Figure 3. W_a and S values with untreated bamboo as substrate.

According to these values, the bamboo-PVDF system is expected to show good adhesion and more or less the same adhesion is expected for PP and MAPP. It has to be noted that these values only relate to intra-molecular forces and do not relate to chemical bonding. Figure 3 also shows the good physical interaction between chitosan and the bamboo surface.

Figure 4 shows the transversal (top) and longitudinal flexural properties (bottom) of MAPP, PP and PVDF bamboo composites made with the same procedure either at 175 °C or 200 °C and with a fibre volume fraction of 40%.

Figure 4. Top – Transversal flexural properties of MAPP, PP and PVDF bamboo fibre uni-directional composites at 175°C and 200 °C. Bottom – Longitudinal properties of MAPP, PP and PVDF bamboo fibre UD composites at 175°C and 200 °C [11].

The calculated values for the work of adhesion correlate reasonably well with the obtained results

for the transversal properties, shown in figure 4. As predicted by the calculated work of adhesion, mechanical test results for PVDF are better than for the other matrices (once the PVDF is properly molten at 200°C), proving that the work of adhesion has really improved.

While 3-point bending tests evaluate the interfacial properties of composites which are often affected by processing conditions (fibre volume fraction, voids, fibre alignment, and inhomogeneties), micromechanical tests could let us evince the importance of physical interactions at the interface in a more clear way. Accordingly, single fibre pull out tests were performed on PP-bamboo and PVDF-bamboo composites with the aim to compare both nonpolar and polar systems.

Figure 5-left shows the dependence of the apparent shear strength on embedded fibre length for the PVDF-bamboo fibre system. The curves were obtained by fitting the experimental data with the Greszczuk model [12]. If compared with PP (Figure 5-right), the observed pattern for PVDF show a more brittle interface fracture behaviour since there is no constant function of apparent shear strength versus embedded length. On the contrary, figure 5-right reveals a more constant shear strength indicating a less brittle interface for PP and bamboo fibre.

Figure 5. Apparent shear strength versus embedded length for PVDF-bamboo fibre (left) and PP-bamboo fibre (right) composites.

The apparent shear strength was calculated according to Eq. 8, assuming that the interfacial loading is a shear mode, there is no friction, the shear stress along the fibre is uniform, and the fibre cross section is circular.

$$\tau_{app} = \frac{F}{\pi DL} \quad (8)$$

where F is the maximum force recorded, D is the diameter of the fibre, and L the embedded length.

Two different interfacial shear strength values for PVDF and PP are shown in table 3. The second column corresponds to the value of apparent shear strength at an embedded length of 0.6 mm, while the first column corresponds to the maximum interfacial shear strength. The latter value is obtained by fitting the experimental data with the model proposed by Greszczuk [12], which assumes that the shear stress is small compared to the matrix strength and that the tensile stress in the matrix is insignificant compared to the fibre. It is evident that higher values are obtained when PVDF is used as a polymer matrix, as predicted by surface energy calculations and confirmed by transverse 3-point bending tests.

Samples	Ultimate interfacial shear strength (MPa)	Apparent shear strength at 0.6 mm (MPa)
PVDF-Bamboo	7.5	8.4
PP-Bamboo	3.4	3.2

Table 3. Results for interfacial shear strength from single fibre pull-out tests [11].

3.3 Bamboo fibre surface treatment

Figure 6 shows the calculated W_a and S values with chitosan-treated bamboo fibers as the substrate. It can be seen that the spreading coefficient is negative for all the systems in the case of chitosan bamboo treated fibers, meaning that there will be problems for impregnation of the treated fibers. Moreover, the work of adhesion is also lower if compared with untreated fibers. The adhesion of the treated fibers will depend on chemical bonding to improve the quality of the interface.

Figure 6. W_a and S values with chitosan treated bamboo as substrate.

Bamboo fibers were coated using a chitosan solution [13]. The purpose of this treatment is to increase the amount of available hydroxyl-groups on the surface. In this way, the properties of MAPP-bamboo composites might be increased, since lignin has fewer hydroxyl-groups at the surface, and MAPP has the capability to form covalent bonds with hydroxyl groups through esterification.

The obtained surface energy results shown in Table 2 for MAPP are very similar to the results obtained for PP. The small differences in values may be created by the presence of the maleic anhydride in MAPP and aging processes.

The calculated work of adhesion of MAPP with chitosan as the substrate (56 mJ/m²) is lower if compared with untreated fibers. So theoretically we would expect lower mechanical properties with chitosan coated bamboo, considering just physical interactions. However, chitosan may increase the presence of hydroxyl groups at the surface and may promote chemical bonding with maleic anhydride, increasing the mechanical properties of the composite. Looking at figure 7, we only see this improvement in the longitudinal direction. We have an increase of 20% of the efficiency factor (according to the rule of mixtures and by considering a tensile strength of 700 MPa for bamboo, 55 MPa for PVDF, 30 MPa for PP, and 18 MPa for MAPP) for the longitudinal strength while the transverse strength remains the same. So, the transversal test does not confirm the improvement of adhesion strength, possibly because of lower transverse strength of the chitosan coating.

The calculated work of adhesion for PVDF with chitosan coated bamboo (59 mN/m) is much smaller than for PVDF with untreated bamboo (75 mN/m). So theoretically one would expect a composite made with bamboo and PVDF to be much stronger than a composite made with chitosan coated bamboo and PVDF, since there are no chemical bonding mechanisms. The results of the three point bending tests correspond with the theory and are shown in figure 7.

For PVDF, the composite with the uncoated fibre is about 30% stronger in the longitudinal direction and about 3 times better in the transversal direction, showing that the adhesion is better in the uncoated fibre. Both composites, with treated and untreated fibres, show about the same longitudinal stiffness, which is around 80% of the theoretical value of 19.2

GPa according to the rule of mixtures, indicating similar levels of wetting.

Figure 7. Top – Transversal flexural properties of MAPP, and PVDF chitosan-treated-bamboo fibre unidirectional composites. Bottom – Longitudinal properties of MAPP, and PVDF chitosan-treated-bamboo fibre UD composites. Percentages give the efficiency factor.

4 Conclusions

Surface energy components and wetting parameters obtained from contact angle measurements are useful tools for evaluating the compatibility of natural fibres and various matrices for making composites. In this way, surface energy components of natural fibres and thermoplastic matrices were matched, resulting in the improvement of the physical adhesion of bamboo fibre composites, confirmed by 3-point bending and pull-out test results. As predicted, PVDF-bamboo fibre composites present the best combination of wetting parameters, showing a high work of adhesion, as well as a positive spreading coefficient helping to achieve a better wetting of the molten polymer on the bamboo fibre.

For MAPP-bamboo composites, no increase in physical adhesion was predicted nor found, compared to PP, but for MAPP-chitosan coated

bamboo an increase in longitudinal strength was observed which, may be attributed to a chemical adhesion mechanism.

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